

THE LINGUISTIC TERMINOLOGY AND WAYS OF FORMING TERMS IN ALBANIAN LANGUAGE TEXTBOOKS, IInd - IXth GRADES

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Abstract:

Terminology, as a system of specific terms is an integral part of every field of knowledge, science, and production activity, but linguistics deals with the identification, procession and the codification of relevant terms within a terminological system. As a concrete field of study, terminology is related to the study of specialized terms used in science, technology, culture, art, medicine. In this paper, we will bring valuable innovation to the development of linguistic terminology and it is observed the ways of building linguistic terms, especially those used in the Albanian language textbooks of primary and secondary education in II-IX grades. Based on these textbooks, but also on the theoretical contributions of native and foreign terminologists it is highlighted the diversity of forms and ways in which linguistic terms are formed, the place they have in our textbooks divided by the relevant disciplines, classes in which they are used and the age of learners. In this paper are considered the most productive tools that provide language scientific terms, classified per its subsystems. This paper also displays valuable scientific contribution to the development of global terminology in general and the Albanian terminology.

Keywords: terminology, textbooks, scientific terms, linguistic

Term and Terminology. A theoretical approach

The efforts for a specialized communication in various fields of knowledge, science and culture have been present since ancient times, but if we refer to the development of modern terminology as a science, it has emerged in the 1930s with the work of the Wuster in Vienna, entitled "*Internationale sprachnormung in der Technik*", VDI, Berlin,

1931. Wuster, has considered the terminology a tool that should be used effectively in the language to avoid the ambiguity in scientific and technical communication. He built a theory of the terminology, based on his terminographic experienceⁱ. Based on the already accepted conception, terminology is a system of terms that represent concepts of a field of knowledge.

Precisely, the totality of these systems of terms, which corresponds to the related fields systems of concepts, constitutes the terminology in the general sense of the word. Per Rey (1995), the terminology is a practice where three features are distinguished: The practice of recognition; the linguistic and social nature. Simultaneously, the cognitive aspect is related to linguistic and social aspects, by building in this way, useful system terms for different fields of knowledge and scienceⁱⁱ.

The Albanian scholar Ferdinand Leka, who has studied the issues of terminology, defines it (terminology), "*as a means of expression and reflection of the scientific and technical terms.*" It is formed in direct connection with the development of science and technology, with the development of material and spiritual culture of a nationⁱⁱⁱ.

Theresa M Cabra outlines some specific definitions for terminology per the interest of scientists from different fields:

- For the terminologists, terminology is a formal reflection of conceptual organization in a certain field and a necessity of the special speech and professional communication.
- For users of terminology, it is a field where the practical communication units are placed. They are designed per a precise and appropriate economic criteria, in science, technique, knowledge, and technology.
- For linguistic implementors, terminology is a field that requires intervention through linguistic mechanisms to ensure the understanding of the terms, their effectiveness, sustainability, and survival, which can be realized through the process of modernization.
- For linguists, the terminology is a part of vocabulary of the language, of lexicon, which is determined by the specific content of the issue, topic, and its pragmatic use^{iv}. Every terminology is already clearly defined as a set of terms, which share the same features that belong to the same environment, by defining the broadening limits per specific fields^v.

ⁱ Wuster. E, *The Machine Tool. An interlingual dictionary of basic concepts*, London, technical Press, 1968

ⁱⁱ Rey Alain, *Essays on Terminology* Translated and editet by Juan C. Sager. Amsterdam & Philadelphia, 1995,

ⁱⁱⁱ F Leka, *Terminologjia tekniko- shkencore dhe gjuha e sotme letrare shqipe*, në Studime mbi leksikon dhe mbi formimin e fjalëve në gjuhën shqipe, V III, Akademia e Shkencave e Shqipërisë, Tiranë, 1989, p 645

^{iv} Teresa M Cabra, *Terminology, Theory, Methods*, 1992, p 10

^v Gouadec Daniel, *Terminologie. Constitution des donnés*, "AFNOR GESTION", Paris, AFNOR, 1990

Let us see how the term is defined in the conceptual level. Cited by Abolfazi Zarnikli, in his work "Towards a model for Terminology Planning (2014), Leitchik and Shelou, after giving the definition of Lotte, that "*the term is a special word*" and from Vinokur that, "*the term is not just a special word, but a word with a special function*", we express their ideas for the term and its condition: "*The term borrows from natural languages, the basic language and its most important feature, which remains in its terminological nature.*" Thus, the term, according Leitchik and Shelou, in other words is "*the ability to model a specific concept in a whole system of concepts within a field of knowledge, science, technology, etc.*"^{vi}

As it is seen from the above-mentioned aspects, the term definitions are different. Thus, the Albanian Language Dictionary of the 2006 definition of the term is given below:

Term, -I SH.-A (T). A labeled well defined and precise notion of a field of science, technology, art, social life, etc., expressed by a word or a phrase that shows a certain notion and is used by a group of people belonging to a profession.^{vii}

While the Albanian researcher Agron Duro, gives another definition for the term: "*The term is a special type of lexical unit, the language denominator and is distinguished from the structural characteristics and from the content as well, as it serves to express scientific and technical concepts*"^{viii}. F Leka continues by saying that "*Special terms especially well processed terminological systems are needed not only to express different notions (concepts) different, but also they help for their acquisition. The suitable term shapes the notion spreads it and makes itto resist time.*"^{ix}. So, the term as an integral unit of a terminological system, has inherent features, accuracy, clarity, conciseness, and the ability to build concepts for the realization of an effective and a specialized communication. While in the lexical aspect, terms are part of a special vocabulary of any language, built with specific vocabulary words and the terminology system has in its use the terminological lexicon which is distinguished for its systematic and organizational character.

How terms are formed?

The process of Terminologism, that is how terms are established, has to do with the use of language, and its lexical means. In this process, the words come from the use of language for general purposes and are relocated to be used for specific purposes, by enabling objects labeling or phenomena in various fields of knowledge and science. Of course, that each language has its own ways and means for the formation of terms,

^{vi} Gouadec Daniel, *Terminologie. Constitution des donnés*, "AFNOR GESTION", Paris, AFNOR, 1990, p.16

^{vii} *Fjalori i Gjuhës Shqipe* (Albanian Language Dictionary), Akademia e Shkencave e Shqipërisë, Tiranë, 2006

^{viii} A Duro, *Termi e fjala në gjuhën shqipe*, Sh. B Fan Noli, Tiranë 2009, p 31.

^{ix} F Leka, *Terminologjia tekniko- shkencore dhe gjuha e sotme letrare shqipe*, në Studime mbi leksikon dhe formimin e fjalëve në gjuhën shqipe, Akademia e Shkencave e Shqipërisë, Tiranë, 1989, p 645.

however, different terminologists have defined some general principles and ways of their formation.

Let's see, how Teresa M Cabra classifies these ways, in her study, *Terminology, theory, methods and applications* (1992) Formation of terms achieved through very good knowledge of the language and its resources. Terminologists, by knowing the language use its tools to build a term which is used for specific purposes. Three methods are generally recognized based on the formation of terms, classified in terms of language use and its resources:

1. Formal Method
 2. Functional Method
 3. Semantic Method
1. In the formal method, are included four ways of how a term is formed:
 - a) The formation of the terms through words to whom are added as morphemes, prefixes, suffixes, or both.
 - b) The formation of terms through the process of forming compound words which must do with the combination of two or more simple words to create a new word not only with semantic value, but with conceptual value.
 - c) The formation of terms using phrasal unities, which are created because of the combination of words organized by syntax.
 - d) The formation of terms through trunk words, which is a formal way that relates to the reduction of a linguistic unit, such as initials, abbreviations, etc.
 2. The functional method includes two ways of term formation:
 - a) The formation of terms through conversion, which involves changing the category of a word without changing its form, where every feature that belonged to the former category, is eliminated, and replaced by features that belong to the new category.
 - b) The formation of terms through lexicalization, which means the conversion of a form of the lexeme in a new word with a new grammatical category.
 3. The semantic method includes two ways the term formation:
 - a) From the form-based origin of the word, where the two main sources are the general vocabulary of the language and the terminology of other special subjects, which is semantically modified per the context in a specialized communication.
 - b) The modification, which is realized through the following forms:
 - c) It adds meaning of a word base form.

It narrows the meaning of a word base form. It changes completely the basic meaning of a word form^x. These methods are universal in every system, regardless of the field of terminological knowledge, science, or engineering. They contain the basic

^x F Leka, *Terminologjia tekniko- shkencore dhe gjuha e sotme letrare shqipe*, në *Studime mbi leksikon dhe mbi formimin e fjalëve në gjuhën shqipe*, Akademia e Shkencave e Shqipërisë, Tiranë, 1989, pp. 92- 95.

principles on terminologists rely on for the design of the terms. These methods and principles are unique for all kinds of terms, which mean that terminological systems are based on their specific function of scientific communication.

Obviously, terminologists in the process of terms formation, should know the rules of a language, especially the grammatical and word formation processes. Concepts, within a subject or field of knowledge, are organized into structures called conceptual systems, which reflect the world, which is brought about through the terminology experts on a field of knowledge and science. These systems consist of several classes of concepts which label classes through specific terms, objects, belonging, interactive links, occurrence, etc.

Ways of forming linguistic terms used in the Albanian language textbooks

The totality of the terms of a terminological field constitutes its vocabulary, thus the total of terms represents the terminological lexicon of the language as a science. Like other terminological systems belonging to different fields of knowledge, the formation ways are the same even for terms and the terminological system of the Albanian language. Being based on the above models of terms formation, let's see some of them: The first layer consists of terms established by the Albanian source.

Because the terminological lexicon may be changed the terms move or are replaced with other words in the lexicon terminology of Albanian language, are noticed terms which are replaced with words of the Albanian source as *the nominative, dative, genitive, accusative, subject, predicate adjective, comma, verb, pronoun, preposition, prefix, suffix, conjunction, adverb, etc.* There were the Renaissance figures, those who realized the creation of these terms from the source of the Albanian language, which were used in textbooks of that period. Even today, the abovementioned terms are used in textbooks and Albanian language primary and secondary education, grade II- IX.

The second layer consists of foreign and international terms. Such terms borrowed from various languages, mainly from Greek, are used not only in the linguistic literature, but also in textbooks. From them we can mention; *antonyms, synonyms, dialect, homonyms, Polysemes, metaphor, metonymy, phonetics, grammar, phraseology, vocabulary, lexicology, syntax, semantics, morpheme, phoneme, etc.* The international linguistic terms are more numerous in the entire terminological lexicon of the Albanian language. They are found in academic texts, scientific studies, while the terms mentioned above are most useful, they are found in the texts of the Albanian language and learners are familiar with them and with their conceptual content every year^{xi}. So, despite the work done for Albanisation linguistic terms, it cannot be considered a radical cleansing of the linguistic terminology the language from the foreign words, because a part of the terminology has an international character which

^{xi} J. Thomai, *Leksikologjia e gjuhës shqipe*, Toena, Tiranë, 2006, pp. 271- 272).

means that it serves as a common code in the specialized communication between specialists from different countries.

As quoted above, another way of forming terms in linguistics is that of forming terms from usual words. There are found a lot of terms formed by this method in our textbooks. We can mention: *analysis (linguistic), the survey (dialectal), core (word, sentence), couple (synonymous), function (the word), field, transitive (verb) channel (of communication), category (grammatical), mood (the verb), construction (syntactic), unit (language), register (language), order (of words), order (grammatical), root (of the word), degree (the adjective, the adverb), person (the verb), compounding (of the word), etc.* These lexical units in the context of the language as a science provide the connection between general and terminological lexicon, by taking conceptual values^{xii}.

Regarding to word formation structure of the term, so the linguistic tools that help to the terms formation, there is another division;

1. The method of forming with prefixes, suffixes, or both. In the Albanian language textbooks, we see many terms formed as *pronoun, adjective, adverb, preposition, particle, determiner, adverbial, impersonal, exclamative (sentence), apposition, auxiliary (verbs), passive voice nominal (group), perfect (tense), (indirect object), inflexion, causative (ways), subjunctive, conjunction, linguistic (dictionary), lexical (fields), prefix, suffix, indirect (speech), conversational, etc.*

2. Compounding formation is the joining of two or more independent words in a single term. Such terms are; *orthography, spelling, question mark, exclamation mark, semicolon, collocation, reflexive (pronoun), pragmatylistics, prefix- suffixes, morfo- syntax, subject, diphthong, consonants, etc.*

3. The third way is by changing the meaning, so in linguistic terminology is saved the word but not its meaning, as the word labels concepts of the linguistic field. As it is mentioned above, in Albanian language textbooks has enough of these word- terms, for example; *family (Word), group (nominal), root (the word), themes (the word), article degree (the adjective, adverb), full stop (punctuation), order (grammatical), etc.*

4. The fourth method is the formation of collocational terms, thus the syntactic method. In every terminological system collocational terms, constitute the majority. Even in linguistics and textbooks which have been analyzed, are noticed terms of this type^{xiii}.

In linguistic terminology and in other terminologies as well, the most prominent phenomenon is that of extending the term “monosyllabic”, which is expanded in other words and creates a new terminological concept through collocations, which enhance the meaning of a word in monosyllabic terms. Such terminological collocations are widely used in textbooks for example with the word “*component*” there are formed a

^{xii} Sh Rrokaj, V. Bello, *Mbi domosdoshmërinë e një fjalori të termave të gjuhësisë në gjuhën shqipe*, në Gjendja dhe zhvillimi i terminologjisë shqipe, probleme dhe detyra, Konferenca shkencore, Tiranë, 2009, p. 171.

^{xiii} H. Pasho & A. Duro, *Terminologjia shqipe- probleme dhe detyra*, në Gjendja dhe zhvillimi i terminologjisë shqipe, probleme dhe detyra, Konferenca shkencore, Tiranë, 2009, Konferenca shkencore, Tiranë, 2009, p. 28.

variety of linguistic collocations, for example; *lexical component, semantic component, word component, phonological component syntactic component, sentence component etc.*, or with the word: "structure" *inner structure, the interior structure, word structure, sentence structure, derivative structure semantic structure, functional structure etc.*

Terminological linguistic collocations can be formed from compound words which have a general use, but take conceptual value within the terminological system of linguistics such as: *internal form, distinctive feature, solidification of the meaning, main clause, independent clause direct order, coordinate connection, conversational analysis, etc*^{xiv}. Agron Duro makes another classification of terms being based on its external form. Per him, it serves as a form- content association. Based on this relation, terms can be divided in authentic, self-identified or mixed terms. By analogy with this division, many can be mentioned.

In the first division (authentic terms), take part terms such as *noun, adjective, adverb, verb, subject, predicate, determiner, conjunction, particle etc.* In the second division (mixed terms) are included terms that receive conceptual value within a field, while outside it, they have a general lexical sense as *field, family, language, group, etc*^{xv}. Thus, the term is identified as a lexical unit that express a special concept, out of every context.

Despite this, the term in its entirety has a restrictive area, which makes it take sense. It is a background that constitutes the term field of use^{xvi}. If we talk specifically about linguistic terms, we can say that in the language subsystems are found many of them, where some terms have an authentic conceptual value only within the context of conceptual language as science, while outside that context they have a simple comprehensive and lexical value. Thus, we can highlight terms: *root, language (speech), mat (the number), biol (plant); full stop, (punctuation mark), geography (point of horizon); articlet (former of the adjective), building (production line), family, languages (words), boil. (animal), field, (lexical), sport (football, basketball, volleyball, chess), farmers (wheat, corn, potatoes, etc.)*. These terms in addition to the general understanding lexical that carry out of the terminological context are used as linguistic terms within this terminological system, which means that their conceptual value, is identified within the respective field, which in this case is the linguistic field.

In the Albanian language textbooks in primary and secondary education (II-IX grades), there are few terms of this type; most of the terms used in them are scientific terms. which means that their terminological meaning is unique and is not used as simple lexical unit in non-terminological contexts. Such terms may be mentioned the names of the main parts of speech; verb, adverb, pronoun, preposition, conjunction, as well as other terms, phonemes, vowels, consonants, syllable, determiner, predicate,

^{xiv} Sh Rrokaj, V. Bello, *Mbi domosdoshmërinë e një fjalori të termave të gjuhësisë në gjuhën shqipe*, në Gjendja dhe zhvillimi i terminologjisë shqipe, probleme dhe detyra, Konferenca shkencore, Tiranë, 2009, pp. 172-174

^{xv} A Duro, *Termi dhe fjala në gjuhën shqipe*, Botime "Fan Noli", Tiranë, 2009, p.35.

^{xvi} Ibid., p.33

subject, direct object, infinitive, participle, modifier, appositions, cases, inflection, conjugation etc. These terms are conceptual explanations belonging to only one field of use, that of linguistics.

So, while the word is related to the meaning as a semantic- linguistic category, the term is related with the specialized meaning, which is seen the same with the concept. So, the term expresses a certain concept within the terminological and conceptual system of a field, in this case of linguistics^{xvii}.

Conclusions

At the end of this article, it can be said that terminological systems in general and the linguistic ones form the basis of the specialized lexicon of the language, through which is realized the specific effective communication.

Through diverse methods of linguistic terms formation, is seen the great terminological wealth of the Albanian language, which is offered to learners through Albanian language textbooks from grade II to grade IX in primary and secondary education according to respective disciplines.

From the observation of the Albanian language textbooks, in primary and secondary education it is noted that mono word terms take the larger part, even in the textbooks of II, III, IV grades. The number of sustainable collocations is relatively small; it begins to increase from grade to grade, with the increase of the linguistic concepts degree of difficulty in various disciplines.

The use of terminological collocations in these textbooks gives a systemic character to the whole linguistic terminology, and creates accuracy, clarity and understanding to the discovery of the contents of the term.

Despite the presence of international terms in the Albanian language terminology, it is clearly seen that national character translated Albanian terms occupy an important place and are acquired in Albanian language textbooks in primary and secondary education.

Albanian Language is already a science with a national character. So the linguistic terminology is shaped over the years by crystalizing inherent features of clarity, scientific accuracy and professional accuracy. Based on the ways and means of linguistic terms formation, Albanian language terminology has a systemic character, which means that each term within the systemic connections occupies a place in the macro-system of notions, by labeling the concept of the relevant field.

^{xvii} A Duro, *Terminologjia si sistem*, Panteon, Tiranë, 2001, p. 23

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